

Correspondence between real numbers and their positional representation in a natural base

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Abstract

It is well-known that positional representation systems often admit multiple representations for the same real value, as expressed by identities such as $0.\overline{9} = 1$. In the following paper, moving from this identity, we introduce a reformulated positional numerical representation system, based on an abstract 4-tuple definition of a positional representation. We then develop several comparison methods, defining various equivalence relations, and an evaluation map into the real numbers, proving its convergence. We then establish two propositions representing the system's fundamental structure, delving into the consequences of the falsehood of their converses. These results provide the foundation for further developments of the system and culminate in a final theorem, which proves the existence of an alternative periodic representation for all non-zero real numbers with a finite positional expansion. Moreover, the final proposition gives a conceptual interpretation of the theorem.

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1 Initial setup

The following paper moves from the well-known identity

$$0.\bar{9} = 1 \quad , \quad (1)$$

which can be proved in several ways. As a first development of (1) we can add an arbitrary $n \in \mathbb{N}$ to both sides,

$$n + 0.\bar{9} = n + 1 \quad . \quad (2)$$

The pattern suggests that, if an infinite sequence of nines compensates the unit difference between two numbers, a few position shift of the radix point can produce a similar result on the fractional expansion of two non-integers.

1.1 A first proof of a specific case

Let $x = 0.\bar{9}$, multiplying both sides by 10:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0.\bar{9} \\ 10x &= 9.\bar{9} \\ 10x - x &= 9.\bar{9} - 0.\bar{9} \\ 9x &= 9 \\ x &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$0.\bar{9} = 1 \quad .$$

Let $x = 0.0\bar{9}$. By recurrence, using the previous result, $0.\bar{9} = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0.0\bar{9} \\ 10x &= 0.\bar{9} \\ 10x &= 1 \\ x &= \frac{1}{10} \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$0.0\bar{9} = 0.1 \quad .$$

These heuristic proofs suggest that an underlying structure can be extended to many numerical sets as for the representations of their elements in an arbitrary positional base. These considerations can be expressed in the following statement.

Conjecture 1. *Every non-zero real number with a finite expansion in an arbitrary natural base $b \geq 2$ admits an alternative representation that ends with an infinite sequence of digits each equal to $(b - 1)$.*

2 Definition of positional representations

2.1 Set of positional representations

Henceforth, \mathbb{N} denotes the set of all natural numbers, excluding zero. We define

$$\mathbb{X} := \left\{ (b, u, \alpha_k, s) \left| \begin{array}{l} b \in \mathbb{N}, b \geq 2, \\ u \in \mathbb{N}, \\ \alpha_k : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, b - 1\}, \\ s \in \{+1, -1\} \end{array} \right. \right\} \quad (3)$$

as the set of all positional representations, where b is defined as the positional base, u as the position of the unit digit, α_k the sequence of digits and s the sign.

2.2 Radix-point representation

We can represent an arbitrary $x \in \mathbb{X}$ by writing out α_k and placing a *radix point* to the right of α_u :

$$s(\alpha_{(1)} \dots \alpha_{(u)} \cdot \alpha_{(u+1)} \dots)_b \quad .$$

Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be the greatest integer such that $\alpha_n \neq 0$. If $n \leq u$, the radix point can be omitted:

$$s(\alpha_{(1)} \dots \alpha_{(u)})_b \quad ,$$

while if $n > u$:

$$s(\alpha_{(1)} \dots \alpha_{(u)} \cdot \alpha_{(u+1)} \dots \alpha_{(n)})_b \quad .$$

2.3 Comparing numerical representations

Numerical representations can be compared using several relations on \mathbb{X} . In what follows, only two of them will be needed.

2.3.1 Omega equivalence relation

We denote by $\pi_n(x)$ the n -th element of the tuple x . Let

$$\Omega := \{(\omega_1, \omega_2) \in \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \mid \pi_n(\omega_1) = \pi_n(\omega_2) \forall n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}\} \quad . \quad (4)$$

We prove now it is an equivalence relation on \mathbb{X} .

Proof.

1. $\forall x \in \mathbb{X}: (x, x) \in \Omega$.

Let $x \in \mathbb{X}$,
since $\pi_n(x) = \pi_n(x) \forall n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, by definition:

$$(x, x) \in \Omega \quad .$$

2. $\forall x, y \in \mathbb{X}: (x, y) \in \Omega \implies (y, x) \in \Omega$.

Let $x, y \in \mathbb{X}: (x, y) \in \Omega$, it follows:
 $\pi_n(x) = \pi_n(y) \implies \pi_n(y) = \pi_n(x) \forall n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$.

By definition,

$$(y, x) \in \Omega \quad .$$

3. $\forall x, y, z \in \mathbb{X}: (x, y) \in \Omega \wedge (y, z) \in \Omega \implies (x, z) \in \Omega$.

Let $x, y, z \in \mathbb{X}: (x, y) \in \Omega \wedge (y, z) \in \Omega$, it follows:
 $\pi_n(x) = \pi_n(y) \wedge \pi_n(y) = \pi_n(z) \forall n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$.

Therefore $\pi_n(x) = \pi_n(y) = \pi_n(z)$. Hence, by transitive property and definition,

$$(x, z) \in \Omega \quad .$$

□

2.3.2 Theta relation

Let

$$\Theta := \{(\vartheta_1, \vartheta_2) \in \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \mid \pi_n(\vartheta_1) = \pi_n(\vartheta_2) \forall n \in \{1, 2, 4\} \wedge \pi_3(\vartheta_1) \neq \pi_3(\vartheta_2)\} \quad . \quad (5)$$

It can be proved, *mutatis mutandis*, that Θ is not an equivalence relation on \mathbb{X} .

3 Connection between representations and real values

3.1 Definition of the evaluation map

Given an arbitrary positional representation $x \in \mathbb{X}$, its real value $\phi(x)$ is obtained by an evaluation map defined as $\phi: \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which, in its standard form, can be defined as

$$\phi(x) := s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \quad . \quad (6)$$

We prove now that given an arbitrary $x \in \mathbb{X}$ its evaluation is real.

Proof. Let $x \in \mathbb{X}$, by (6):

$$\phi(x) = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \quad .$$

Then, by splitting the sum,

$$\phi(x) = s \left(\underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^u \alpha_k b^{u-k}}_{\in \mathbb{R}} + \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \right) \quad .$$

Since u is finite by definition, the first sum converges to a real value. Moreover, since by definition $0 \leq \alpha_k \leq (b-1) \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$, it can be briefly proved that the second sum is bounded.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} 0 \cdot b^{u-k} &\leq \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \leq \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} (b-1) b^{u-k} \\ 0 &\leq \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \leq (b-1) \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} b^{u-k} \\ 0 &\leq \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \leq (b-1) b^u \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{b}\right)^k \end{aligned}$$

Since $b \geq 2 \implies \frac{1}{b} < 1$, the geometric series converges.

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \leq (b-1) b^u \frac{1}{b^{u+1}} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{b}} \\ 0 &\leq \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \leq (b-1) b^u \frac{1}{b^{u+1}} \frac{b}{b-1} \\ 0 &\leq \sum_{k=u+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

Finally the second sum converges as well and as a consequence $\phi(x) \in \mathbb{R}$. □

3.2 Positional representation propositions

Two propositions can now be stated.

Proposition 1.

Let $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$, then

$$(x, y) \in \Omega \implies \phi(x) = \phi(y) \quad .$$

Proof. Let $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$: $(x, y) \in \Omega$, by definition

$x = (b, u, \alpha_k, s)$ and $y = (b, u, \alpha_k, s)$. Therefore,

$$\phi(x) = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \text{ and } \phi(y) = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k}.$$

Hence,

$$\phi(x) = \phi(y) \quad .$$

□

Proposition 2.

Let $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$, then

$$\phi(x) \neq \phi(y) \implies (x, y) \notin \Omega \quad .$$

Proof. Let $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$: $\phi(x) \neq \phi(y)$. By contradiction, assume that $(x, y) \in \Omega$, then by Proposition 1 $\phi(x) = \phi(y)$. This leads to a contradiction, hence

$$(x, y) \notin \Omega \quad .$$

□

By means of a single counterexample we prove now that the converses of Propositions 1 and 2 do not hold.

Proof. Let $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$ and assume,
 $x = (b_1, u, \alpha_k, s), \quad y = (b_2, u, \alpha_k, s),$
 $\alpha_k = 0 \forall k \in \mathbb{N}, \quad b_1 \neq b_2.$

Since b_1, b_2 are two different bases, $(x, y) \notin \Omega$. Evaluating x and y using (6),

$$\phi(x) = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k u^{u-k} = 0 \quad ,$$

$$\phi(y) = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k v^{u-k} = 0 \quad .$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x) = \phi(y) &\not\Rightarrow (x, y) \in \Omega \quad , \\ (x, y) \notin \Omega &\not\Rightarrow \phi(x) \neq \phi(y) \quad . \end{aligned}$$

□

4 Further notes about Propositions 1 and 2

4.1 Considerations about Proposition 1

It is well-known that given a function $f : \mathbb{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ it is injective if $\forall x, y \in \mathbb{A}: f(x) = f(y) \implies x = y$. However, by the converse of Proposition 1, given two arbitrary $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$

$$\phi(x) = \phi(y) \not\Rightarrow (x, y) \in \Omega \quad .$$

Hence, $\phi(x)$ is *non injective*. This implies that different numerical representations can yield the same real value.

4.2 Considerations about Proposition 2

It has been proved in Section 3.2, by means of a trivial counterexample, that given two arbitrary $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$

$$(x, y) \notin \Omega \not\Rightarrow \phi(x) \neq \phi(y) \quad .$$

However, several non-trivial $x \in \mathbb{X}$ can be used as counterexamples to the converses of Proposition 1 and 2.

4.2.1 Null representations

First, we prove that given an arbitrary $x \in \mathbb{X}$ such that $x = (b, u, \alpha_k, s)$,

$$\phi(x) \neq 0 \iff \exists \varphi \in \mathbb{N}: \alpha_\varphi \neq 0 \quad . \quad (7)$$

Proof. Let $x \in \mathbb{X}: \phi(x) \neq 0$. By contradiction, assume that $\nexists \varphi \in \mathbb{N}: \alpha_\varphi \neq 0$, therefore $\alpha_k = 0 \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$. Consequently,

$$\phi(x) = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 0 \cdot b^{u-k} = 0 \quad .$$

This leads to a contradiction, hence

$$\phi(x) \neq 0 \implies \exists \varphi \in \mathbb{N}: \alpha_\varphi \neq 0 \quad .$$

Let $x \in \mathbb{X}$ such that $\exists \varphi \in \mathbb{N}: \alpha_\varphi \neq 0$,

$$\phi(x) = s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} = s \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\varphi-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_\varphi b^{u-\varphi} + \sum_{k=\varphi+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \right) \quad .$$

Where, as stated in Section 3.1, $\phi(x) \in \mathbb{R}$.

Since, by definition, $\alpha_k \geq 0 \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$, $b^{u-k} > 0 \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$ and, as assumed, $a_\varphi > 0$, it follows that $\phi(x) \neq 0$. Hence,

$$\exists \varphi \in \mathbb{N}: \alpha_\varphi \neq 0 \implies \phi(x) \neq 0 \quad .$$

□

A set of *non-zero representations* can be defined as follows,

$$\mathbb{X}^* := \{x \in \mathbb{X} \mid \phi(x) \neq 0\} \quad . \quad (8)$$

4.2.2 Finite representations

We define,

$$\bar{\mathbb{X}} := \{x \in \mathbb{X} \mid \exists h \in \mathbb{N}: \alpha_h \neq 0 \wedge \alpha_k = 0 \forall k > h\} \quad (9)$$

as the set of all *finite positional representations*. It is worth observing that $x \in \bar{\mathbb{X}} \implies x \in \mathbb{X}^*$.

4.2.3 Alternative periodic representation theorem

At this point, the following theorem can be stated.

Theorem 1. (Alternative Periodic Representation)

Let $x \in \bar{\mathbb{X}}$, $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{X}^*$ such that

$x = (b, u, \alpha_k, s)$ and $\bar{x} = (b, u, \gamma_k, s)$, where

$$\gamma_k = \begin{cases} \alpha_k & \text{if } k < h \\ \alpha_k - 1 & \text{if } k = h \\ b - 1 & \text{if } k > h \end{cases} \quad .$$

Then $\phi(x) = \phi(\bar{x})$.

Proof. By the hypotheses of the theorem and by directly verifying the conclusion,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x) &= \phi(\bar{x}) \\ s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} &= s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \gamma_k b^{u-k} \\ s \left(\sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h} + \sum_{k=h+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k b^{u-k} \right) &= s \left(\sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \gamma_k b^{u-k} + \gamma_h b^{u-h} + \sum_{k=h+1}^{\infty} \gamma_k b^{u-k} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h} &= \sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + (\alpha_h - 1) b^{u-h} + \sum_{k=h+1}^{\infty} (b-1) b^{u-k} \\
\sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h} &= \sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + (\alpha_h - 1) b^{u-h} + (b-1) b^u \sum_{k=h+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{b}\right)^k \\
\sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h} &= \sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + (\alpha_h - 1) b^{u-h} + (b-1) b^u \frac{1}{(b-1) b^h} \\
\sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h} &= \sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h} - b^{u-h} + b^{u-h} \\
\sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h} &= \sum_{k=1}^{h-1} \alpha_k b^{u-k} + \alpha_h b^{u-h}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Notice that $(x, \bar{x}) \in \Theta$, so the following proposition holds:

Proposition 3.

Let $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$, then

$$(x, y) \in \Theta \not\Rightarrow \phi(x) \neq \phi(y)$$

This means that even if two representations have different digits, they could still yield the same real value. Finally, we can state that Conjecture 1 is true.